

The isolated complex was analysed for metal and Chlorine contents.

Baush and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer for absorbance measurements and Parkin-Elmer infra cord spectrophotometer for Infra-red spectra were used.

Result and Discussion

Nature of chelate: Mixtures containing equal proportions of manganese chloride and lawsone were mixed and the absorbance measured⁶. The absorption maximum of the complex (wine red in colour) was found to be at 480 nm.

Composition of the chelate: The composition of the chelate was established by the method of Joh's continuous variation⁷, Molar ratio⁸ slope ratio⁹, and Dey¹⁰. A large number of observations were taken at 480 nm. and it was found that the ratio of Mn^{2+} ; lawsone in the chelate is 1:1.

Evaluation of stability constant and Free energy: The stability constant calculated from the absorbance data by molar ratio method is 3.6×10^5 and free energy formation as calculated from $-\Delta F = RT \ln K$ is -7.6 K. Cals/mole.

Molecular Formula of the chelate: From analysis it was found that amount of Mn in the chelate is 12.1% and amount of Chlorine is 7.8% which correspond to the formula $[(C_{10}H_6O_8) Mn^{2+} (C_2H_5OH)_4] Cl^-$ calculated values are 12.3% for Mn and 7.9% for chlorine.

Structure of the chelate: The O-H band at 3125 cm^{-1} in the ligand completely disappeared in the complex indicating thereby that proton is liberated during complex formation. The lowering of C=O stretch of the ligand from 1650 cm^{-1} to 1630 cm^{-1} in the complex indicates that Co-ordination of lawsone is through carbonyl oxygen.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, I. I. P. Dehra Dun for providing I. R. Spectra of these compounds.

References

1. B. D. JAIN and S. P. SINGAL., *Current Sci.* India, 1962 **31**, 279.
2. A.P. ZOZULYA and V. M. PESHKOVA., *Zhur, Neorg, Khim.* 1959, **4**, 379.
3. I. H. SIFFERT and W. C. PURDY., *J. Electroanal Chem.* 1966, **11**, 302.
4. M.K. AKHMADLI, A.A. SADYKHOVA, P.B. GRANOVSKAYA, I. S. LOZOVSKAYA and S. ALIEVA., *Azerli Khim. Zh.*, 1963, **5**, 93.
5. S. S. SAWHNEY., Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1972.
6. B. S. GARG, R. P. SINGH and M. KATYAL., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.* 1971, **34**, 17.
7. S. K. BANERJI and A. K. DEY., *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1961, **30**, 179.
8. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES., *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* 1944, **16**, 111.
9. A. F. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1950, **72**, 4488.
10. DEY, *Nature Lond.*, 1956, **158**, 95.

Studies on Indian Medicinal Plants-Part XXXIV* Triterpenes from *Grewia asiatica*

SUBHAGATA CHATTOPADHYAY and S. C. PAKRASHI*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry
Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-700032.

Manuscript Received 6 February 1975; accepted 22 March 1975

THE recent report¹ on the isolation of β -sitosterol, β -amyrin and betulin from *Grewia asiatica* Linn(Syn. *G. subinaequalis* DC)^{2,3}, N. O. Tiliaceae, prompted us to publish our work on the stem-bark of the same species. We, however, encountered friedelin, betulin, lupeol and lupenone.

Experimental

All m. p. s. are uncorrected and $[\alpha]_D$ measured in $CHCl_3$. Silica gel was used for column chromatography. The identity of compounds were established by direct comparison (m. p., m. m p, $[\alpha]_D$, tlc and ir) with authentic specimens. The analytical data were in good agreement with the theory.

Dried and milled stem-bark (2 kg) of *Grewia asiatica* was successively extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with light petrol, C_6H_6 and CH_2Cl_2 .

The light petrol extract on concentration separated a yellow solid (fraction A) which was filtered and the filtrate evaporated (Fraction B). The fractions were separately chromatographed.

From fraction A, light petrol- C_6H_6 (3:1) eluted an oil (fraction A₁) while the same solvent mixture (1:1) afforded lupeol (5g), m. p. 212° - 214° , $[\alpha]_D^{+27^\circ}$ in colourless needles ($CHCl_3$ -MeOH); acetate (C_6H_6 - $CHCl_3$), m. p. 215° , $[\alpha]_D^{+47^\circ}$. Further elution with C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 (1:1) yielded betulin (3 g), m. p. 254° - 256° , $[\alpha]_D^{+21^\circ}$ in colourless needles (C_6H_6 -MeOH); dibenzoate, (C_6H_6 -MeOH), m. p. 178° - 179° , $[\alpha]_D^{+37^\circ}$.

Elution of fraction B with light petrol- C_6H_6 (3:1) gave an oil (fraction B₁) followed by lupeol.

The combined oily fractions A₁ and B₁ (0.5 g) was rechromatographed. Light petrol eluted an oil (0.1 g) which crystallised (EtOH) in colourless short stout needles, m. p. 170° - 171° , $[\alpha]_D^{+61.5^\circ}$, ν_{max} 1705, 1640, 890 cm^{-1} , identified as lupenone. Further elution with the same solvent yielded a solid (0.1g) crystallising (EtOH) in colourless needles, m. p. 260° , $[\alpha]_D^{-25^\circ}$; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$ 1710 cm^{-1} identified as friedelin.

On similar chromatographic resolutions, the C_6H_6 extract yielded lupenone (0.011 g), lupeol (0.023 g) and betulin (0.01 g) while the CH_2Cl_2 extract afforded lupenone (0.012 g) and lupeol (0.05 g).

References

1. K. C. JOSHI, L. PRAKASH and R. K. SHAH., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 830.
2. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 128.
3. B. N. SASTRI., "The Wealth of India, Raw Materials", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, vol. IV, p. 262.

* For Part XXXIII in the Series See E. ALI V. S. GIRI and S. C. PAKRASHI *Phyto Chemistry*, (in the press).
To whom all correspondences to be addressed.